

Comparative Analysis of Spiking Neuron Models in SpikeYOLO

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Abstract—This study compares spiking neuron models (Integrate and Fire (IF), Leaky IF (LIF), Parametric LIF (PLIF)) within SpikeYOLO for neuromorphic object detection using the Gen1 automotive dataset. Through systematic evaluation including τ sweep experiments (0.2-3.2), while IF neurons achieve computational efficiency with 8.9% less training time and 7.8% lower energy consumption than LIF neurons, LIF neurons provide superior biological plausibility and analog circuit compatibility through natural membrane leakage dynamics. The three models maintain comparable detection accuracy ($mAP@50-95$: 0.414 vs 0.417). Remarkably, detection performance remains completely stable across all τ values tested, indicating robust temporal parameter independence. These findings suggest that the SpikeYOLO implementation can tolerate significant parameter variations without compromising object detection accuracy, providing valuable insights for practical SNN deployment.

I. METHODOLOGY

Experiments were conducted using the SpikeYOLO architecture on the Gen1 automotive detection dataset, with consistent training parameters across all configurations: batch size of 15 and 50 epochs, and event streams discretized into 4 time steps (T parameter in SpikeYOLO). The experimental setup used dual Intel Xeon Silver 4314 CPUs, 125 GiB RAM and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU, with energy consumption measured using the CodeCarbon library. Experimentation tasks included:

- **Neuron Model Comparison:** Three neuron types were evaluated with default parameters, MultistepLIF ($\tau = 2.0$), MultistepIF (no leakage) and MultistepPLIF with learnable parameter w , where $\frac{1}{\tau} = \text{Sigmoid}(w)$. The PLIF model enables automatic optimization of time constants across network layers.
- **Temporal Parameter Analysis:** A comprehensive τ sweep was conducted with LIF neurons using exponentially distributed values (0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2) to investigate the relationship between temporal dynamics and both detection performance and energy consumption. Additional experiments included using the mean τ value derived from PLIF training (1.6258) and a hybrid configuration combining PLIF encoders with fixed τ LIF neurons.

II. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Table I shows the accuracy and power consumption of the three compared neuron models: IF, LIF and PLIF.

TABLE I
NEURON MODEL PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Neuron	Time (h)	Energy (kWh)	mAP@50-95
IF	28.98	11.02	0.414
LIF	31.55	11.88	0.417
PLIF	33.45	12.29	0.417

The comparative analysis reveals context dependent advantages for each neuron model. IF neurons exhibit computational efficiency characteristics suitable for resource constrained digital implementations, requiring 8.9% less training time and 7.8% lower energy consumption compared to LIF neurons. However, this efficiency comes with the trade

off of reduced biological plausibility due to the absence of membrane leakage dynamics.

LIF neurons provide a balanced approach, offering essential biological realism through natural membrane leakage while improving comparable detection performance compared to IF neurons. This biological plausibility makes LIF neurons particularly suitable for neuromorphic hardware implementations that rely on analog circuit dynamics.

PLIF neurons, despite their adaptive capabilities through learnable time constants, demonstrated the highest resource requirements without corresponding performance gains in this spatial feature extraction task, suggesting that the adaptive benefits may be more pronounced in higher temporal processing scenarios or higher number of epochs. Table II results how accuracy and power consumption changes among different exponential τ values for the LIF neuron model.

TABLE II
 τ SWEEP RESULTS SUMMARY

τ Value	Time (h)	Energy (kWh)	mAP@50-95
0.2	32.88	11.88	0.417
0.8	32.74	11.47	0.417
1.6	32.73	11.46	0.417
3.2	32.63	11.44	0.417

The τ sweep experiments reveal remarkable stability in detection performance, with all tested values (0.2-3.2) achieving identical mAP@50-95 of 0.417. This finding indicates that SpikeYOLO’s architecture exhibits inherent robustness to temporal dynamics variations, which has significant implications for practical neuromorphic deployments. Energy consumption remained consistently stable (11.4-11.9 kWh) across all τ configurations, further supporting the architecture’s parameter independence.

These preliminary results demonstrate that while IF neurons offer good computational efficiency for digital implementations, LIF neurons provide the most suitable balance between biological plausibility and analog circuit compatibility for neuromorphic hardware systems. The choice of neuron model and temporal parameters has minimal impact on detection accuracy within the SpikeYOLO framework. Focus could be then set to analysing the impact of T parameter in the preprocess of the Gen1 dataset in SpikeYOLO. This work opens a required line of research on tuning relevant event based parameters such as T .

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